

Stability Constants of Trivalent Yttrium, Lanthanum Praseodymium and Neodymium Complexes with Alizarin Reds: A Potentiometric Study

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Potentiometric studies on the free ligand and the metal complexes of Y(III), La(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) with Alizarin-Red S were carried out in aqueous medium. The stability constants of these complexes formed were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique, as used by Irving and Rossotti at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.05M (NaClO₄).

THE review of the literature shows that a very few complexes of Alizarin-Red S have been studied potentiometrically¹⁻³, while extensive work has been carried out on spectrophotometric studies. However, the stability constants of Lanthanons have not been reported so far.

In the present communication, the "Practical" proton ligand stability constants and metal-ligand stepwise stability constants at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.05 M NaClO₄ are reported. The stability constants of the ligand complexes so obtained were computed by the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{4, 5} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁶.

Experimental

Materials

Standard solutions of the metal perchlorates were prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of metal oxide (Johnson and Matthey) in perchloric acid. Excess of perchloric acid was removed by evaporating the solution three or four times with double distilled water. A known quantity of perchloric acid was added, before making up the volume, so as to prevent any hydrolysis.

The stock solution (0.02 M) of Alizarin-Red S (BDH, England) was prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity in double distilled water.

Sodium hydroxide was prepared as usual in carbon dioxide free double distilled water and was standardized with standard potassium hydrogen phthalate.

A 0.1 M perchloric acid (A.R., Merck) was prepared by diluting a calculated quantity of it with double distilled water and was standardized with standard sodium hydroxide.

Sodium perchlorate (0.5 M) and potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M) were prepared as usual by dissolving a requisite quantity in double distilled water.

Potassium hydrogen phthalate was used as a standard buffer for the standardization of pH-meter.

Apparatus

A pH-meter with a glass-calomel combined electrode. A thermostatically controlled water bath with the temperature accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The solutions were stirred continuously during the titration.

Bjerrum-Calvin titrations

Three mixtures were prepared as follows:—

Mixture A : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid

Mixture B : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid

+ $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand

Mixture C : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid

+ $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand

+ $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal.

Appropriate quantities of 0.5 M sodium perchlorate was added to each of these mixtures so as to keep ionic strength constant (0.05 M NaClO₄). The final volume in each mixture was adjusted to 100 ml. with double distilled water. The ratio of the metal and ligand was always 1 : 5.

Stoichiometry

The stoichiometry of the metal-ligand complexes formed were determined potentiometrically at 30°. Mixtures containing various metal:ligand ratio were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution. The total volume in all the systems was 100 ml. Figure 3 gives the nature of the graph of pH against the mole fraction of alkali to ligand.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants

The values of \bar{n}_A at different pH -values were obtained from the acid and ligand titration curves. The equation (1) was used to determine the value of \bar{n}_A at a particular pH .

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \{(V'' - V')(N + E^0)\} / (V^0 + V') T_{Cl}^0 \quad \dots (1)$$

The values of \bar{n}_A so obtained were plotted against the corresponding pH -values, (Fig. 1) and proton-ligand stability constants were obtained by method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A -values⁶ which are tabulated in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Formation curve for proton-ligand (at temperature 30° ionic strength 0.05 M NaClO₄).

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ALIZARIN-RED S AT 30°, AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.05M (NaClO₄)

Constants		
log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log β ^H
4.60	11.20	15.80

Metal-ligand stability constants

The stepwise stability constant of complex is given by the equation (2) :

$$K_n = C_{MLn} / C_{MLn-1} \cdot C_L \quad (\text{where } n = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_n is called the n th metal-ligand stability constants.

In the present work, the stepwise stability constants were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL , where, \bar{n} is the average number of ligands attached per metal ion and is given by the equation (3) :

$$\bar{n} = (V''' - V'')(N + E^0) / (V^0 + V') \bar{n}_A \cdot T_{CM}^0 \quad \dots (3)$$

where, T_{CM}^0 is the total concentration of the metal in the system while other terms have their usual meanings. pL is the free ligand exponent given by the equation (4).

$$pL = - \frac{\log \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{n=j} B_n^H (1/\text{antilog } pH)^n V^0 + V''' \right\}}{\{(T_L \bar{C}^0 - \bar{n} T_{CM}^0) \bar{V}^0\}} \quad \dots (4)$$

where β_n^H is the overall proton-ligand stability constant.

It was observed that, the values of \bar{n} in the case of Y(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) exceeded 1.5 while in the case of La(III) it did not go beyond 1.5 thereby indicating that only 1 : 1 complex is formed in this case, while in other three cases 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complexes are formed. The stepwise metal-ligand stability constants for the different metals, at 30°, and at an ionic strength of 0.05 M (NaClO₄) are tabulated in Table 2 below :

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 30° AND AT AN IONIC STRENGTH μ = 0.05M (NaClO₄)

Metal	Constants		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
Y(III)	12.68	11.14	23.82
La(III)	11.77	—	11.77
Pr(III)	12.56	8.90	21.46
Nd(III)	12.73	8.90	21.63

Stoichiometry

In establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species with Alizarin Red S, two inflections were observed. First inflection is observed at $m \approx 0.5$ while second one appears at $m \approx 1.00$. The appearance of the first inflection after addition of half a mole of base per mole of ligand corresponds to the neutralization of the first hydroxyl proton while the appearance of the second inflection after addition of one mole of base per mole of ligand accounts for the neutralization of the second hydroxyl proton. Thus, both the protons of the two hydroxyl groups are neutralized by one mole of the base per mole of ligand. The reaction occurring during the interval of $m \approx 0$ to 1.00 can be given in terms of combined equation as :

Thus, three ligand species H₂ARS, HARS⁻, and ARS⁻² exist in equilibrium in the pH -range corresponding to the values of $m \approx 0$ to 1.00.

Addition of equimolar concentrations Y(III) ions (Fig. 3, Curve B) greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation but the stoichiometry could not be concluded from this curve since precipitation occurred during the titration; which indicates that hydroxyl ions

dominate the ARS^{2-} ions in forming complex species with Y^{3+} ion. But when Y(III) to ARS ratio is 1 : 2 (Fig. 3, Curve C), the curve shows inflection at

Fig. 2. Formation curve for Y-ARS (at 30°, at an ionic strength 0.05 M NaClO_4).

$m \approx 2$ indicating the formation of $\text{Y}(\text{ARS})_2^-$. The equilibria can be given as :

The formation of the complex $\text{Y}(\text{ARS})_3^{3-}$ is evidenced by the inflection at $m \approx 1.67$ when the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 3 (Fig. 3, Curve D). The equilibrium is given as :

From Table 2 it is clear that Y(III), Pr(III), and Nd(III) forms 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complexes while La(III) forms only 1 : 1 complex. The stability of the complex is in the order $\text{Y}(\text{III}) > \text{Nd}(\text{III}) > \text{Pr}(\text{III})$ for 1 : 2 complexes.

Fig. 3. Stoichiometry of Y-ARS :
 System A : $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ ligand
 System B : $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ ligand + $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ metal
 System C : $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ ligand + $3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ metal
 System D : $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ ligand + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ metal

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References

1. L. HAVELKOVA and MILOS BARTUSEK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1969, **34**, 3722.
2. A. VARADARAJULU and U. V. SESHAIHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 1065.
3. PRADIP K. GOVIL and SAMIR K. BANERJI, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, (Taipei), 1972, **19**, 83.
4. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution" (Haase : Copenhagen, 1941).
5. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
6. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.